

Electrometric Studies on the Composition and Stability of Thallium (III) Complexes of β -Mercapto-Propionic Acid

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The Tl(III) complexes of β -Mercapto propionic acid have been investigated by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques in aqueous 0.1 M KNO_3 . It was found that Tl(III) forms two colourless complexes; 1 : 1, predominating at pH 4.0-5.0 and another 1 : 2 at pH 6.0-8.5. The stability constants of these complexes have been determined at three different temperatures by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. The log K values (final) for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes computed by alternative methods at 20, 30 and 40° have been found to be 10.13 ± 0.09 , 10.54 ± 0.03 , 10.83 ± 0.13 and 7.96 ± 0.22 , 8.21 ± 0.10 , 8.58 ± 0.09 respectively. The values of overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the reaction have also been evaluated at 30° and found to be -25.9 k-cal/mole, 27.8 k-cal/mole and -6.2 cal/deg/mole respectively.

In the sphere of the coordination chemistry, the interest has recently been focussed on the complexes of different metal ions¹⁻⁷ with mercapto acids and other sulphhydryl compounds, owing to the presence of an active—SH group available for coordination. In our earlier publications⁽⁸⁻¹¹⁾, investigations on the composition, stability constants and thermodynamic functions of the complexes of metals such as Ag^+ , Zn^{++} , Ni^{++} , Tl(I) with thiomalic acid have been reported. In view of the interesting results obtained earlier, it was considered worth while to extend similar investigations on the complexation of β -mercapto propionic acid (referred to herein as MPA) with various metal ions. This contribution describes a potentiometric and conductometric study of Tl(III)-MPA system, which involved the computation of successive stability constants by alternative methods (convergence formulas of successive approximations, least square treatment, correction term method), the effect of temperature variation on the stabilities of the complexes and the determination of overall changes in free energy, enthalpy, and entropy accompanying the reaction. No reference could, however, be traced out in the literature on the study of Tl(III) complexes of MPA, their stability constants and other thermodynamic functions. The current study has therefore been undertaken.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. β -Mercapto-propionic acid (99.1% Evan's Chemetics, Inc. New York) and AnalaR (B.D.H.) reagents TiCl_3 , KNO_3 , NaOH etc. were used and their solutions prepared in air free conductivity water. An approximately $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ solution of MPA was prepared and standardised by potentiometric titration with standard NaOH . $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ solution of TiCl_3 was prepared by direct weighing of analytical grade thallic chloride. The freshly prepared aqueous solution of TiCl_3 was stable and does not hydrolyse. However, the hydrolysing tendency occurred in very dilute solutions but was completely checked by the presence of ligand.

Equipment. A Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) $p\text{H}$ meter with universal glass and calomel electrodes was used for $p\text{H}$ measurements and calibrated by using several solutions 10^{-2} and $10^{-3} M$ HClO_4 with ionic strength 0.1M (obtained by the addition of NaClO_4). Thus the reading gave immediately concentrations and not activities of H^+ . Before and after each series of measurements, a calibration was made. Though the meter can measure 0.01 unit of $p\text{H}$, it is supposed that with the error inherent in calibration, the ultimate error is ± 0.02 $p\text{H}$ unit.

The conductance measurements were carried out by means of an electronic eye type conductometer (LBR; W.T.W. Germany).

Procedure. The experimental procedure involved a series of $p\text{H}$ and oconductometric titrations of MPA with standard NaOH in the absence and presence of Tl (III) at various ligand to metal ratios. All the $p\text{H}$ -titrations were performed in aqueous 0.1M KNO_3 .

The potentiometric titration assembly consisted of a water jacketed pyrex vessel of 200 ml capacity fitted with a rubber bung, having holes to accommodate the tube delivering nitrogen, thermometer, a microburette and Cambridge universal glass and calomel electrodes. The temperature was controlled by circulating water from Universal Thermostat Type U3 (VEB PRUFGERATEWERK MEDINGEN/DRESDEN) bath through the water jacket. A CO_2 free nitrogen atmosphere (pre saturated with 0.1 M KNO_3) was maintained above the solution throughout the titrations.

For each measurement, the known volumes of the standard solutions of MPA, TiCl_3 , and KNO_3 were added in the reaction cell with microburette and the total volume of the titrating solution was made upto 30.0 ml with water. Care has been taken to prevent the hydrolysis of TiCl_3 solution by adding it after the addition of ligand, while preparing titrating solutions. The contents of the titration vessel were purged with nitrogen for five to ten minutes. After the thermal equilibrium had been established, the electrodes were inserted and the titration begun. The base was added in small increments which were further decreased in the regions of rapidly changing $p\text{H}$ values. It has been noted that the equilibrium $p\text{H}$ was reached almost instantaneously.

The possibility of reduction of Tl(III) by the addition of MPA has been ruled out in a separate experiment (based on the quantitative precipitation of thallos ion as Tl_2CrO_4 by K_2CrO_4) under nitrogen in a four-legged test tube : one leg contained Tl(I) (from an aqueous solution of TlNO_3), the second contained TiCl_3 , the third MPA and the fourth K_2CrO_4 . The

contents of the legs were mixed in the order listed : 1+4 gave characteristic yellow precipitate of Tl_2CrO_4 , 2+4 gave a light orange colour and 3+4 also gave orange coloured clear solution.

In another set of experiment, one leg contained $Tl(I)+MPA$, the second contained $Tl(III)+MPA$, the third contained $Tl(III)+Tl(I)+MPA$ and the fourth K_2CrO_4 . These solutions were again mixed in the following order : 1+4 gave the yellow precipitate of Tl_2CrO_4 , 2+4 gave the same orange colour and 3+4 gave the yellow precipitate of Tl_2CrO_4 and hence indicated the presence of $Tl(I)$. The absence of precipitate in second leg, indicates that no $Tl(I)$ is present as a result of the reduction of $Tl(III)$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry. The stoichiometry of the reaction between $Tl(III)$ and MPA was determined by potentiometric and conductometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard alkali.

Figure 1 represents the pH and conductometric titrations of solutions $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ in MPA (curves 1 and 5), $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ in MPA and $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ in $TlCl_3$ (curves 2 and 6), $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ in MPA and 1.66×10^{-3} in $TlCl_3$ (curves 3 and 7) and $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ in MPA and $1.11 \times 10^{-3}M$ in $TlCl_3$ (curve 4) with $0.1M$ NaOH. The abscissa represents the moles of NaOH added per mole of ligand 'a'.

The appearance of only one inflection (Fig. 1, curve 1), after one mole of base per mole of ligand has been added, corresponds to the neutralisation of the single carboxyl hydrogen. Hence, if free MPA, having two replaceable hydrogen ions is denoted as H_2SA , the reaction between 'a' interval of 0-1 may be represented by the equation.

The addition of equimolar concentration of $Tl(III)$ ions (Fig. 1, Curve 2) greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of complex formation and consequently a considerable shift in the position of the end point is indicated. The fall in the initial pH value and the lowered buffer region between $a = 0-2$ clearly shows the displacement of the proton due to complexation. Since the extent of proton displacement depends on the relative affinities of the ligand for hydrogen ions and the metal ions, it is obvious from the curve that the interaction of $Tl(III)$ with MPA is sufficiently great that the metal ion can compete with hydrogen ion for the ligand even at relatively low pH , and hence a considerable lowering in buffer region starts, showing finally two inflections at 2 and 3 moles of base per mole of ligand. The inflection at $a = 2$, suggests the formation of $TlSA^+$, which may be shown by the equation.

Further reaction with another mole of hydroxyl ion is indicated by the fact that $Tl(III)$ titration curve has an additional buffer region and a second inflection at $a = 3$. Thus the second reaction step, indicated by the inflection at $a = 3$ may be associated with the formation of higher complex or the neutralisation of proton from the water molecule coordinated to the metal ion to form the hydroxo metal complex—the case which is usually visualized

with the partially chelated metal ion. However, the formation of higher complex would result in the disproportionation of TlSA^+ with the formation of higher complex $\text{Tl}(\text{SA})_2^-$ and thallic hydroxide and hence the inflection at $\alpha = 3.5$. The fact that no precipitation occurred throughout the titration and the absence of inflection at $\alpha = 3.5$ eliminate this possibility and suggest that the second reaction step involves the neutralisation of hydrogen from the coordinated water molecule in accordance with the equation

to form hydroxo complex $\text{TlSA}(\text{OH})$ in which both the ligand and the hydroxyl ion are coordinated to the metal.

When two moles of Tl^{3+} are added to the ligand (Fig. 1, curve 3), the curve shows only two inflections, first at $\alpha = 1.5$ and second at $\alpha = 2$, which correspond to the stepwise formation of TlSA^+ and $\text{Tl}(\text{SA})_2^-$ respectively. The reaction equilibria may be expressed as

The stepwise formation of these two complexes have been further confirmed by the inflections at $\alpha \approx 1.33$ and 1.66 (Fig. 1, curve 4) even when the ratio of metal to ligand has increased to 1 : 3.

Conductometric Studies. Figure 1, (curves 5, 6 and 7) represents the changes in conductance when solutions of MPA were titrated against NaOH in the absence and presence of $\text{Tl}(\text{III})$. In such conductometric titrations where the weak acid was neutralised by a strong base, the shape of the titration curve depends on the concentration and dissociation

Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Potentiometric (curves 1-4) and conductometric (curves 5-7) titrations of MPA in the absence and presence of $\text{Tl}(\text{III})$ with 0.1 M NaOH .

Curves 1 and 5. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M MPA}$

Curves 2 and 6. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M MPA} + 3.33 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M TlCl}_3$

Curves 3 and 7. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M MPA} + 1.66 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M TlCl}_3$

Curve 4. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M MPA} + 1.11 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M TlCl}_3$

constants of the acid. The curves show a minimum, because when NaOH is added progressively to a solution of MPA, the salt formed during the first part of the reaction tends to repress the ionisation of the acid still present so that its conductance decreases. The rising salt concentration will, however, tend to increase the conductance and owing to these opposing influences, the titration curves show a minimum. As the titration proceeds, break at $a = 1$ (Fig. 1, curve 5) was obtained and beyond which the graph becomes linear.

Fig. 1, curve 6, for the solution containing 1 : 1 ratio of MPA to Tl(III) shows two breaks at $a = 2$ and 3, corresponding to the formation of TlSA^+ and $\text{TlSA}(\text{OH})$ in accordance with the equations (2) and (3) respectively.

Fig. 1, curve 7, for a solution containing MPA and TlCl_3 in the ratio of 2 : 1 shows two breaks at $a = 1.5$ and $a = 2$ which confirm the formation of TlSA^+ and $\text{Tl}(\text{SA})_2^-$ respectively (equations 4 and 5).

These results are similar to those obtained by potentiometric methods demonstrating the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

It may be particularly pointed out that polynuclear complex is not formed because \bar{n} is a function of $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ only (which has been tested by obtaining measurements at various metal ion concentrations) and is independent of the total metal ion concentration.

Computation of Stability Constants : Calvin and Melchior's¹² extension of Bjerrum's¹³ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes from potentiometric

Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of MPA in the absence and presence of Tl(III) with 0.1 M NaOH at three different temperatures.

Curves 1, 3 and 5. 3.0 ml M KNO_3 + 1.8 ml M/5 HCl + 5.0 ml M/50. MPA (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 20°, 30° and 40° respectively.

Curves 2, 4 and 6. 3.0 ml M KNO_3 + 1.8 ml M/5 HCl + 5.0 ml M/50 MPA + 1.0 ml M/50 TlCl_3 (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 20°, 30° and 40° respectively.

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titration data. The two successive reactions of complex formation may be represented by the following expressions

The overall stability constant β is given by

$$\beta = \frac{[\text{Tl}(\text{SA})_2^-]}{[\text{Tl}^{3+}][\text{SA}^{2-}]^2} = K_1 K_2 \quad (8)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the formation constants of the reactions (6) and (7) respectively.

The procedure used for calculating the stepwise stability constants of Thalliothioacetate complexes was similar to that adopted to earlier publications⁸⁻¹¹. The evaluation of \bar{n} , which is defined as the average number of ligand molecules bound per mole of metal, was made from figure 2, which represents the potentiometric titrations of MPA with standard alkali in the absence and presence of Tl(III) at three different temperatures. No precipitation of Thallio hydroxide was observed during any of these titrations. At any $p\text{H}$, the horizontal distances between curves 1-2, 3-4 and 5-6 (corresponding to 20, 30 and 40° respectively) measure quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of SA^{2-} complexed. This number divided by total $[\text{Tl}(\text{III})]$ gives \bar{n} . At any $p\text{H}$, $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ was calculated as

$$[\text{SA}^{2-}] = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{SA}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{TISA}^+] - 2[\text{Tl}(\text{SA})_2^-]}{\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_{a_1}K_{a_2}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_{a_2}} + 1} \quad (9)$$

where K_{a_1} ($pK_{a_1} = 4.38$) and K_{a_2} ($pK_{a_2} = 10.38$) are the first and second dissociation constants of the acid. All quantities in equation (9) are known and thus a series of \bar{n} and $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ values at various $p\text{H}$ were obtained at different temperatures and formation curves were plotted (Figure 3, curves 1, 2 and 3). The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were read directly

Fig. 3. Plot of \bar{n} as a function of $-\log[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ at three different temperatures.

Curve 1. at 20°.

Curve 2. at 30°.

Curve 3. at 40°.

from the graph at \bar{n} values of 0.5 and 1.5 respectively and were found to be 10.15 and 7.99 (at 20°); 10.53 and 8.23 (at 30°); 10.91 and 8.62 (at 40°) respectively. These values of successive stability constants were further refined by the following methods :

(1) Convergence formulas of successive approximations¹⁴; (2) Least Square treatment¹⁵; (3) Correction term method¹⁵.
and shown in Table 1.

TABLE I

Method	20°			30°			40°		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
Extension of Bjerrum's method	10.15	7.99	18.14	10.53	8.23	18.76	10.91	8.62	19.53
Schroder's convergence formulas	10.04	8.09	18.13	10.52	8.23	18.75	10.90	8.62	19.52
Least Square	10.18	7.74	17.92	10.55	8.11	18.66	10.70	8.49	19.19
Correction term	10.14	8.05	18.19	10.57	8.26	18.83	10.81	8.61	19.42
Mean	10.13	7.96	18.09	10.54	8.21	18.75	10.83	8.58	19.41

THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) on complex formation have been determined at 30°. The expression¹⁶

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta \quad (10)$$

relating overall stability constant β to the total free energy change of the reaction, was employed for evaluating the value of ΔG , which was found to be -25.9 K-cal/mole.

The value of ΔH was determined with the help of isobar equation¹⁶ given as follows :

$$d \ln \beta / dT = \Delta H / RT^2 \quad (11)$$

where T is the absolute temperature and R is the gas constant and may be conveniently written in the form

$$d \log \beta / d(1/T) = \Delta H / 4.57 \quad (12)$$

The mean value of $\log \beta$ (from Table-I) obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $(1/T)$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 30° was determined and equated with $-\Delta H/4.57$. The value of ΔH thus obtained was found to be -27.8 K-cal/mole.

The overall entropy change (ΔS) of the reaction was calculated from the equation¹⁶

$$\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G) / T \quad (13)$$

and found to be -6.2 cal/deg/mole.

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The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of two complex species $TlSA^+$ and $Tl(SA^-)_2$ in the pH range 4.0–5.0 and 6.0–8.5 respectively. The logarithms of the successive stability constants were found to be 10.13 ± 0.09 and 7.96 ± 0.22 (20°); 10.54 ± 0.03 , 8.21 ± 0.10 (30°) and 10.83 ± 0.13 and 8.58 ∓ 0.09 ($40^\circ C$) respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS evaluated at 30° were found to be -25.9 K-cal/mole, -27.8 K-cal/mole and -6.2 cal/deg/mole respectively.

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